

A Comparative Study Of Health Consciousness Among Various Department Students In S.R.T.M.U. Nanded.

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Abstract

Physical education is intended to strengthen one's health and harmoniously develop the body. It improves one's physical attributes and skills, helps develop and perfect motor skills necessary in everyday life and work, and eventually leads to physical perfection. Health is the level of functional or metabolic efficiency of a living organism. In humans it is the ability of individuals or communities to adapt and self-manage when facing physical, mental or social challenges. Physical education in India is often a neglected part of education and many schools across the country do not realize the importance of having physical education as a part of the system. A comparative study of health consciousness among various department students of S.R.T.M. University Nanded". Physical education is that part of general education program which is concern with growth, development and education of children through the medium of muscular activities. Physical education helps in the development of physically, mentally, emotionally and moral development of the student.

Introduction

Physical education is a social and pedagogical process constituting an organic part of general upbringing. Physical education is intended to strengthen one's health and harmoniously develop the body. It improves one's physical attributes and skills, helps develop and perfect motor skills necessary in everyday life and work, and eventually leads to physical perfection. The basic methods of physical education or physical exercises (specially selected natural movements and series of movements, for example, those used in gymnastics and track and field), various sports, and hardening of the body (using healthful nature forces, such as sun, air, and water). Also important are the observance of healthful habits at work and in daily life and the mastering of special knowledge and skill for exercising, hardening the body, and maintaining personal and public hygiene. The goals, content, organization, and methods of physical education, which are conditioned by socioeconomic structure, reflect class ideology.

Health is the level of functional or metabolic efficiency of a living organism. In humans it is the ability of individuals or communities to adapt and self-manage when facing physical, mental or social challenges.

Health Consciousness: meaning

Health is the overall condition of an organism at a given time. Thinking of people, health consists of a complete state of physical, social, and mental wellbeing. Health permits people to lead an individually, socially and economically productive life. Health consciousness is the basic concept of living a healthy life that makes sure that you do not get sick and are able to live an optimal life style.

- It can provide every one freedom from all diseases
- It can provide sound mental and physical state to live optimal life.
- It helps you choose your health care options.
- According to the World Health Organization (WHO) report, it is a fundamental human right.

Significance of the Study: Findings of the study will be helpful to determine the health consciousness of the students.

Objectives of the Study: To measure the general motor ability and the healthy living among four various faculty of S.R.T.M.U. Nanded

Methodology

Source of Data:

The data pertaining to this study were collected from the four faculties of S.R.T.M. University Nanded. These are as under:

Pharmacy, Math, Social science, Educational science

Selection of Subject: This student selected through simple random sample method and researcher selects the 100 subjects, 25 from each faculty.

Approach towards physical activity and physical fitness scale:

Standard questionnaire namely "Health consciousness questionnaire" was used to know about the health consciousness of the students of four various faculties of S.R.T.M. University Nanded. The questionnaire consists of 20 questions. The questions are in the form of open type and every question has four answer options, which are Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), Strongly Disagree (SD)

Statistical Tools:

The obtained data has been put to statistical analyzed to determine the significance differences in the level of general motor ability and healthy living. Mean, S.D and analysis of correlation value have been computed to compare the score on each item. The whole statistical analysis was done by using Statistical Package for Social Sciences. (SPSS)

**Table No – 1,
Indicates the Mean, S.D. and Std. Error in general motor ability of Social Science, Math's,
Pharmacy and Educational Science.**

Exercise	Mean	S.D.	Std. Error
Social Science	17.28	1.563	0.313
Maths	17.84	1.617	0.323
Pharmacy	16.52	2.402	0.480
Edu. Sciences	16.88	2.422	0.484

Table-1 shows the statically analysis of Mean, S.D. and Std. Error in general motor ability of Social Science, Math's, Pharmacy and Edu. Science. So, mean, S.D. and Std. Error of social science is 17.28, 1.563 and 0.313. In the same way mean, S.D. and Std. Error for math is 17.84, 1.617 and 0.323. Mean, S.D. and Std. Error for pharmacy is 16.52, 2.402 and 0.480. Mean, S.D. and Std. Error for Edu. Science is 16.88, 2.422 and 0.484.

**Table No -2,
Indicates the Mean, S.D. and Std. Error in Healthy Living of Social Science,
Math's, Pharmacy and Educational Science.**

Healthy Living	Mean	S.D	Std. Error
Social Sciences	14.4	1.855	0.371
Maths	15.36	1.622	0.324
Pharmacy	13.92	1.896	0.379
Edu. Sciences	15.08	1.718	0.343

Table-2 shows the statically analysis of Mean, S.D. and Std. Error in Healthy living of Social Science, Math's, Pharmacy and Edu. Science. So, mean, S.D. and Std. Error of social science is 14.4, 1.855 and 0.371. In the same way mean, S.D. and Std. Error for math is 15.36, 1.622 and 0.324. Mean, S.D. and Std. Error for pharmacy is 13.92, 1.896 and 0.379. Mean, S.D. and Std. Error for Edu. Science is 15.08, 1.719 and 0.344.

Table No -3,
Analysis of variance of healthy living among various faculty students

Source variance	df	Sum of the squares	Mean of squares	F-ratio	Sig.
Between group	3	31.950	10.650	3.241	.025
Within group	96	315.440	3.286		

*Significant at .05 level
($f=3.241, p<.05$)

Show the statistically significant difference of healthy living among various faculty students. As above observed in F-ratio was 3.24 at 0.05 level of significance.

Results: The findings of this study show that there was:

- Statistical significant difference of general motor ability at 0.05 level between students of math and pharmacy faculty. Hence research hypothesis is accepted.
- Statistical significant difference of healthy living between students of math and pharmacy faculty. Hence research hypothesis is accepted.
- Statistical significant difference of healthy living between students of pharmacy and educational science faculty. Hence research hypothesis is accepted.

Conclusion:

- Within the limitations of the study and from the statistical analysis the following conclusion is drawn:
- The study shows the statistic mean difference i.e. 1.32 of general motor ability between students of math and pharmacy faculty.
- The study shows the statistical significant mean difference i.e 1.44 of healthy living between students of math and pharmacy faculty.
- The study shows the statistical significant mean difference i.e 1.16 of healthy living between students of pharmacy and educational science faculty.

Recommendation of the study:

1. This study may helpful for the current U.G. and P.G. students.
2. The study will be helpful to understand the importance of physical education for mankind.
3. The study will be helpful for the students in competitive sports.
4. The study will be helpful to the teachers to guide students towards physical education.
5. The study will be held on the various subjects students also.

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